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An integrated approach to management development: A framework for practice and research

ABSTRACT

Human performance is instrumental in achieving organizational objectives; management development (MD) has been evident in organizations as an important tool to enhance individual and team performance. The organizational dimensions that influence MD operate in an integrated fashion and influence the way MD is perceived, how it is positioned, and how it is managed within the wider organizational context. This paper proposes that MD should be closely integrated with seven key dimensions; MD research should not only be concentrated on the MD component itself, but also on the relationships that it has with these dimensions. The implications of the proposed framework on theory and practice are also discussed.

Keywords: management development, strategy, human resource planning, performance management

INTRODUCTION

Management development puts particular emphasis on the development of comprehensive, coordinated, and dynamic approaches for managerial learning initiatives within and outside an organisation in order to facilitate the achievement of corporate objectives in a competitive environment. It is based on the supposition that managerial learning must be treated by organisational policy makers as a deliberate business process rather than an accident. For MD to be accomplished, there should be a coherent set of policies and practices, which collectively serve to ensure that learning is embedded in the fabric of the organisation to the benefit of all stakeholders.

The paper proposes a conceptual framework depicting interactions MD has with seven key dimensions with which MD should complement and reinforce each other, being a building block of a larger human resource plan that is developed to facilitate the achievement of corporate objectives. The paper is organized into two sections. The first section reviews

relevant literature and presents the conceptual framework. The second section addresses the implications of the framework on theory and practice and presents research areas for further inquiry and understanding.

MANAGEMENT DEVELOPMENT

Organizations today are facing complex, rapidly changing, and in some respects unprecedented environments. In order to be effective and efficient, organizations must continuously adjust their internal configurations, such as structure, technology, work process, and culture (Sun, 2000). Organizational development is a set of conceptions and techniques that can be applied to improve organizational, group, and individual capabilities and effectiveness (Beer and Walton, 1987; Doorewaard and Benschop, 2003; Francis, 2003). Human resource development (HRD), on the other hand, is concerned with development and change through learning, giving emphasis on how, what, and where individuals learn as individual learning remains the foundation of learning within organizations (Elkjaer, 2001; Grey and Antonacopoulou, 2007; Walton, 1999). The focus of HRD is on capabilities that individuals need in order to operate and cooperate effectively in an organizational context (Megginson et al., 1993). The literature highlights that there has been a limited critical review and the development of HRD theory in the past two decades (Simmonds and Pedersen, 2006). In particular, since the inception of the term HRD in the early 1980s, there has been a dichotomous approach developed to HRD. On one side of the Atlantic, the Americans pursued a performance outcomes paradigm, which focused on developing individuals to enhance organizational performance outcomes (Swanson and Holton, 2001). Much of the American approach emerged through organizational development theory (DeSimone et al., 2002). On the other side of the Atlantic, the British have pursued a learning and development paradigm that focused on enhanced training and development genres (Garavan et al., 1999). In this context, management development (MD) has been accepted as an important means of developing managers.

It is accepted that competitive advantage is internal to the organization, not external as was once thought (Longenecker and Ariss, 2002; Ulrich and Lake, 1990). In today's business environment, high-quality managers are valuable, rare, difficult to imitate, and not subject to substitution. If managed effectively, they are the most expensive and valuable assets of an organization (Rausch et al., 2002; Wright and Ferris, 1996). Hence, the development of this asset is crucial to the success of any organization. In the international context, learning,

knowledge acquisition, and adaptation are important rationales for the creation of international businesses that contribute significantly to international business performance (Lyles and Salk, 1996). Hence, MD efforts continue to be an essential element for organizations striving for excellence and need to invest wisely in this strategic asset. Organizations can adopt two approaches to enhance managerial capabilities, i.e., organizations can buy skills through selection or can improve the quality of the current employees by providing comprehensive HRD programmes after selection (Delaney and Huselid, 1996). In the latter case, considerable evidence suggests that investment in strategically focused MD offers more flexible and long-term advantages by signaling the choice of a value-added business strategy (Kirkbride, 2003; Longenecker and Ariss, 2002; Shefy and Sadler-Smith, 2006; Storey and Sisson, 1993). On the other hand, individuals whose skills are at a premium can expect several career shifts in their lifetime, wherever that might be, as the old psychological employment contract based on “trust” is breaking down (Kim, 2005; Walton, 1999). Hence, the challenge for organizations is to generate commitment for the duration of an individual’s stay by offering opportunities to develop. This creates a relationship, which brings mutual benefit for both parties. This relationship, on one hand, maximizes the contribution that employees can make to the organization and, on the other, enables them to maximize their own development (Bugshaw, 1996). Hence, the cycle between individual and corporate interest is squared by a new relationship. Organizations are committed to the development of individuals. In return, individuals plough back what they have learned into the organizations. This continues for as long as the contact lasts. Permanence has gone. A new kind of mutual growth has taken its place. In this context, provisions for learning can increase the level of commitment of managers to the organization and increase their perceptions that the organization is a good place to work (Belling, 2004; Schuler, 1987). Hence, learning has evolved into a new role that calls for balancing the interests of the employees with those of the organization (Bender et al., 1996). Being understood the value of learning, the theorists and practitioners suggest that organizations should actively undertake measures to develop their managers.

In developing managers, organizations could use two processes, namely informal and formal. Informal MD processes are by-products of organizational activities, such as task accomplishment and interpersonal interaction, and managers may not set out intentionally and explicitly to learn something through pre-planned means (Holden and Hamblett, 1998; Järvinen and Poikela, 2001; Marsick and Watkins, 1997; Mumford, 1997). Formal MD processes, on the other hand, are institutionally sponsored, planned, and deliberate processes, which are often

monitored and controlled by people and forces other than the individual manager involved (Marsick and Watkins, 1997; Mumford, 1997). Evidence reveals that informal processes were often seen by managers as preferable to various forms of formal MD processes (Mumford, 1997). There can be several reasons as to why managers often find informal processes more effective than formal ones, such as, development programmes designed as off-the-job processes are experienced as unreal, irrelevant to the manager's priorities, or difficult to transfer the learning to actual work environment; processes of learning attached to formal MD processes reflect interests of programme designers and do not take into account different individual learning preferences (Akuratiyagamage, 2004; Griffin, 2003; Rees and Porter, 2005).

However, there are some deficiencies in the total reliance on a single process - formal or informal (Akuratiyagamage, 2004). On one hand, simple reliance on informal processes is not claimed to be the best answer for MD. Informal processes are both insufficient and inefficient, because managers most often lack the skills to make the most of the learning experiences. On the other hand, formal MD processes are important but insufficient and often inefficiently provided. Therefore, it is not the view that formal MD processes are necessarily better than informal MD processes. Nor is it the view that simply because informal MD processes are, in a sense, both natural and inevitable, that they should be relied on to the exclusion of formal MD processes. Therefore, the separation of formal MD processes from informal MD processes literally takes MD away from the reality of managerial work (Malcolm et al., 2003). Thus, the integrated approach to MD should make judicious use of both processes and should be integrated in terms of time, mental application, and even physical circumstances with managers' normal work activities (Akuraiyagamage, 2004; Lohman, 2006). The effectiveness of both processes depends to a very large degree on the organization's climate, which is conducive to learning, where learning is deliberately encouraged, nurtured, and supported (Akuratiyagamage, 2004; Belling et al., 2004; Muhamad and Idris, 2005; Rodwell, 2005).

Management development as a concept and as a practical discipline reveals a concern to demonstrate appropriate structural and functional relationships with other areas of human resource management (HRM) (Maclagan, 1992; Shefy and Sadler-Smith, 2006; Walton, 1999). Rothwell (1996) state, "...if MD operates as an isolated, solitary activity that is not linked with other organizational initiatives and policies, it often involves the so called 'sheep dip' approach, where nothing else happens to reinforce MD and often expectations about the outcomes it

achieves are limited to getting individuals to attend” (as in Megginson et al., 1993). Hence, MD is an integrated and holistic approach to facilitate, guide, and coordinate learning, using a range of learning techniques and strategies (Megginson et al., 1993; Walton, 1999). This integrated perspective is based on the supposition that MD should be treated as a deliberate business process, and it differs markedly from the traditional approach focusing on the individual level outcomes (Arthur, 1994; Burack et al., 1997; Napier, 1996; Walton, 1999).

PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

The main dimensions with which MD should be integrated are strategy, top management attitudes towards MD, job analysis, performance appraisal, human resource planning (HRP), and succession planning. First, MD needs to be seen as a part of the strategy development process of a given organization. *Strategy*, both organizational and HRM, affects the way MD is perceived. The relevance of the MD content is enhanced when there is an obvious connection between the objectives of MD and the strategies of the organization, as such a connection enhances the continuity between learning and results in the organizational context. *Top management attitudes towards MD*, on one hand, are seen as capable of creating, maintaining, and changing the norms governing the attitudes of human resource managers and other senior functional managers towards MD, and their behaviours when dealing with the development needs of managers. On the other hand, top management attitudes could also be affected by MD and would, in turn, help to shape their attitudes. *Job analysis* provides job descriptions and specifications, which should be used as inputs to performance appraisal as well as to the MD. *Performance appraisal* information, used in conjunction with job analysis information, determines the development requirements to improve current and future performance. Organizations find it increasingly necessary to provide MD programmes to develop managerial talent. This demands that the MD be derived from the organizational objectives and strategies, projected human resource demand, and the anticipated internal supply. *HRP and succession plans* help to formalise this necessity and articulate the concern for effectively utilising management talent now and in the future. Above all, an MD should be able to balance the *expectations of both the organization and its managers*. Thus, the two main explicit outcomes of MD should ultimately be the achievement of MD objectives and increased organizational performance, and the achievement of expectations of managers from MD. Based on this proposition, Figure 1 is drawn to show MD and its interactions with strategy, top management

attitudes towards MD, job analysis, performance appraisal, HRP, and management succession that are critical to the success of MD.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework for Integrated Approach to MD

Organizational Strategy and HRM Strategy

Strategy denotes an activity that organizations perform in order to accomplish their goals (Bratton and Gold, 1999). Strategy influences MD, and strategy is influenced by MD. With regard to the influence of strategy on MD, the traditional belief that HRD strategy should be considered only after the strategic business decisions are made is no longer valid (Wright and Ferris, 1996). In this context, for MD to become “strategic,” it needs to be seen as a part of the strategy development process of any organisation, since the organisation is dependent on effectively utilising and enhancing all of its resources to cope with current and future contingencies (Kirkbride, 2003; Longenecker and Ariss, 2002; Luoma, 2005). It should provide a range of solutions to organizational problems and ensure that human resource capabilities are considered in both the determination of goals and the assessment of organizational capabilities (Fulmer et al., 2000; Rausch et al., 2002; Tichy, 2002). In this regard, MD has to be undertaken with full strategic intent with an understanding of how MD initiatives over a longer period add to the coherence and are congruent with an explicit learning philosophy incorporated into the organizational mission (Walton, 1999). MD strategy should provide the long-term orientation,

while MD policies express an organization's commitment to the continuous development of managers to maximise their contribution as well as to assist them to advance in their careers. To achieve these, it is essential that MD integrates with the organisation's overall strategy and encompasses the performance and reward management processes of the organisation; ensure that how these are applied and interpreted enables and encourages learning and development to take place.

With regard to the influence of MD on strategy, MD influences strategy in several ways. First, organizational strategies are sustained by culture and management style. MD implicitly or explicitly propagates and creates characteristic organizational cultures, and reinforces one another insofar as they support a particular culture (Fombrun 1984; Hendry, 1995). Second, strategic plans and strategic decisions depend on the quality of the management and the organizational decision-making processes. MD contributes to the quality of managers over time (Hendry, 1995). Finally, successful business strategies are developed around the core competencies of the organization, rather than being driven primarily by the assessment of market opportunity (Hendry 1995). Thus, MD can provide input concerning the availability of the required human resources (quantity and quality) and the costs of acquiring, retaining, developing, and motivating such resources since these frame the possibilities for a business (Hendry 1995).

Top Management Attitudes towards MD

Top management commitment is the key to the success of MD. Hall (1984) states, "perhaps the most important factor in ensuring that MD is done strategically is the participation of top management in the process. Because top management is the strategic level of the organization, and because top management represents the strategic business planners of the organization, they should also be the human resource planners. Top management should be involved in planning and executing MD" (p176). Further, Schuler (1987) notes "without top management support and commitment to MD, the major focus of an organization is likely to be on activities other than MD. This is particularly true when the focus is on short-term goals and immediate results, which allows too little time to wait for the benefits of MD" (p396). Furthermore, Purcell (1995) points out "if top management does not support MD and if the financial control mode and short-term investment criterion dominates, there would be a trend to drive out long-term MD investment and destroy the basis of MD as a part of the corporate strategy" (in Bratton and Gold, 1999 p50). A recent study conducted in Malaysia also emphasized the role and support

of top management in MD (Muhamad and Idris, 2005). However, top management's attitudes and their willingness to share decision-making could influence the degree of participation of human resource managers in the strategy process (Devanna et al., 1984; Mumford, 1997).

Top management could construct an organizational culture that reflects their ideologies and styles of management, which will reinforce their strategies and control (Bratton and Gold, 1999; Hendry, 1995). For this, top management could use MD to send out messages about what is acceptable and desirable behaviour. Top management could use several unwritten and unspoken channels to influence MD, which are capable of creating, maintaining, and changing human resource managers' and other functional managers' attitudes and behaviours when dealing with MD. Some of such channels are the budget and time allocated for MD, the status given to resource personnel connected to MD, the frequency of MD programmes being moved to other locations to make room for other business activities, the frequency of MD programmes are postponed or cancelled because of other business activities, the frequency of managers are pulled-off from MD programmes because of other official engagements, the standard of the facilities provided for MD, and the frequency of managers are allowed to get promotions before they have been adequately developed (Wills, 1998).

Therefore, on one hand, it is difficult to ignore the influence that top management could have on MD, and on the other hand, it is difficult to separate the strategy from top management. Therefore, MD should establish support from top management, ensuring that the organization is prepared to support and nurture the new competencies that MD is capable of creating.

Job Analysis

An organization's mission and work processes determine the jobs it needs to accomplish its objectives; each job has an associated set of duties and requirements. Job analysis is a systematic procedure of gathering, documenting, and analysing information about jobs in an organization. Based on job analysis information, job descriptions and specifications are produced. Job description identifies the overall purpose of a job, the content of the job, the context in which the job is performed, responsibilities, accountabilities, the reporting relationships of the job holder, career prospects, and opportunities to acquire new skills/expertise (Armstrong, 2004; Veres III et al., 1996). Job specification identifies the job requirements in terms of skills, abilities, the areas of knowledge, experience, personality, interests, and physical and other characteristics that an individual must possess to perform the

content of the job to achieve an acceptable level of performance (Armstrong, 2004). Therefore, job analysis provides a clear indication of the particular requirements of the job, where that job fits into the overall organization structure, and a description of the kind of person who should be hired for the job. Job analysis information needs to be utilized in the identification of MD needs, the selection of MD programmes, and the evaluation of MD programmes. The proper use of job analysis information ensures that the appraisal instruments assess what is actually being done on the job (Mathis and Jackson, 1994). Hence, job analysis could be identified as the *sine qua non* for virtually all HR planning, development, and performance appraisal activities carried out by organizations.

However, when the world of work is undergoing changes, the types of jobs needed also tend to change (Sparrow, 2000; Styhre, 2006). According to Stewart and Carson (1997), modern organizations are moving beyond hierarchical structures and controls toward flexible, network-oriented, team-based designs. Hence, the contemporary organizing perspective assumes that work activities are structured around people and that a person's role is largely dependent on the particular contracts an individual enters (Stewart and Carson, 1997). The trend towards relational organizing should thus be accomplished by reduced reliance on the results of objective job analysis. These fundamental changes in the nature of work create many problems and questions (Peterson et al., 2001). In this context, Stewart and Carson (1997) stated that while the legal environment currently implies that businesses conduct some type of job analysis, the degree to which participants agree about and actually follow job analysis depends on the extent to which the structure is based on evolved relationships rather than hierarchical relationships. In this context, MD is one particular facet of contemporary organizations that is in need of a new perspective and job analysis, as a part of the MD is an understudied area.

Performance Appraisal

Performance appraisal provides a basis for the analysis of an individual's record of accomplishment by evaluating how well individual performed the requirements of the position he/she occupy, and isolates performance deficiencies and provide feedback on how to make the best use of the abilities, realise the potential and maximise the contribution to the success of the organisation (Abraham et al., 2001; Boland and Fowler, 2000; Mumford, 1997). In this regard, Performance appraisal can be used for three purposes, namely, developmental appraisal, maintenance appraisal, and remedial appraisal. Developmental appraisal is future-oriented and focuses heavily on spotting employees who are likely to do well on more

challenging jobs, and on providing developmental opportunities to help ensure they will do well. In contrast, remedial appraisal is more present-oriented and seeks to spot current performance deficiencies, analyse the reasons for them, and then design programmes to remove them. Maintenance appraisal is concerned with maintaining current employee performance levels (Schuler, 1987, p 278).

When viewed from a systems perspective, job analysis provides vital information to conduct performance appraisal successfully. If appraisal is conducted successfully, it is perhaps the most central HR function in that it provides vital data for rational, objective and efficient decision making impacting on other HR system components such as personnel selection, diagnosing MD needs, identifying potential, managing careers, setting levels of reward and evaluating the effectiveness of work design interventions (Austin, et al., 1996; Boland and Fowler, 2000; Mumford, 1997; Verweire and Van den Berghe, 2003). For instance, a well-functioning performance appraisal scheme drives MD. When an individual receives clear feedback on his/her performance, the individual's second question (after asking 'how did I perform?') will be, 'how can I perform better?' Learning to perform better requires the sharpening and acquisition of knowledge, skills, and abilities - in short, development (Hall, 1984). Therefore, along with the performance appraisal scheme, a scheme for long-term performance improvement and development is vital. In this regard, performance appraisal also provides information to evaluate the effectiveness of the past MD programmes that an individual had been provided with. Further, future human resource projections depend on the assessments of the performance potential of existing individuals, for which performance appraisal is capable of. Such information should be used as an input to the HRP and succession plan. Hence, a logical starting point for the management succession scheme is the information provided by the performance appraisal scheme (Tichy et al., 1984). Therefore, efforts to strengthen the links between appraisal and other dimensions would contribute to the overall success of corporate strategic plans.

Human Resource Planning and Management Succession Planning

The idea of "cradle to grave" careers is no longer relevant in the more changeable managerial job markets of today, and everyone cannot be promoted through the organization's hierarchy. In this context, the term "career" is extended to apply not only to movements through pre-defined stages but also to personal growth by establishing routes to take and time frames to meet through an individual's interaction with the work environment. Human resource planning

(HRP) and management succession plans are tools that should be used for this purpose (Armstrong, 2004; Hendry, 1995; Jackson and Schuler, 1996). HRP involves forecasting an organization's future human resource demand in terms of numbers and characteristics and formulating and implementing programmes through staffing, appraising, compensating, and HRD to ensure that individuals are available when and where the organization needs them (Ferris and Buckley, 1996; Jackson and Schuler, 1996).

Management succession plans are also designed to safeguard the long-term health of an organization. Those could be used to review business strategy with its changing goals and priorities as a means of pinpointing the key competencies required of employees. While many companies have given up on traditional succession planning, no successful business can stop identifying and developing the right people to ensure that the important skills are present in the organization to compete effectively and achieve superior results over the long term. In the circumstances, it will not, however, focus on specific jobs. Instead, the focus will be on the skills and strategies required to achieve the desired business results (Stephen and Guinn, 2000). However, a well-developed HRP and succession plan will not work on its own. The findings of a Korean study by Kim (2005) revealed that organizations need to design career systems or performance incentive systems in accordance with employees' different career success orientations.

Achievement of Expectations from MD

When considering the prime beneficiary of MD, one approach is to see the organization as the prime beneficiary where MD is work-oriented, performance-driven, organization-centred, and organization-sponsored effort. As the purpose of MD is to ultimately contribute directly to the organization's goals through improved performance, MD has no meaning unless a connection is made to organizational performance (Swanson and Arnold, 1997). Organizations do not receive immediate return on the time managers spend on MD programmes, yet the growth of the organizations demands upgrading managerial skills (Fulmer et al., 2000; Lawler et al., 1995; Luoma, 2005). Therefore, the communication of organizational expectations should be a part of the MD process to ensure that MD is realistic and adds value to the organisation (Warren, 1979).

The other approach is to see individuals as the prime beneficiaries where MD enables them to maximise their own personal development and ensures that, in a business world of constant

flux, they are always employable and thus have their own personal security (Bugshaw, 1996; Walton, 1999). The provision of MD can increase individuals' perception that the organization is a good place to work (Walton 1999). This is a part of a wider phenomenon whereby individuals increasingly see organisationally sponsored acquisition of competencies as a reward -even an inducement- in its own right and a means to secure future employability. MD, thus, becomes a part of the organisation's reward structure apart from its contribution to increased organisational performance (Walton 1999). If MD runs in isolation, not linked with other dimensions such as selection, performance appraisal, management succession, and rewards, frustration and negative attitudes would develop (Hendry 1995). Since there are differences in the organization's expectations and the individual's expectations from MD, it is critical that the expectations are identified and clarified before an MD programme begins. An appropriate follow-up support would indicate the extent of the achievement of the expectations (Belling et al., 2004).

IMPLICATIONS OF THE CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

There is a limited number of studies conducted on conceptual and empirical grounds on the dimensions discussed in the framework. On empirical grounds, both survey-based research and case studies have generated a limited conceptual and empirical support for the proposed integrated approach to MD. Though research has been focused on individual dimensions such as performance appraisal and succession planning, there is a lack of empirical studies on the interconnection between those. Therefore, it could be said that the structural and functional relationships MD has with other areas have been neglected. On practical grounds, there is a need to use more human resource information in the strategy formulation. Though many organizations invest a considerable amount of resources in MD programmes, the majority of those organizations do not examine how their MD programmes address the business plans. In some instances, HRM function is not involved in formulating business strategy from the outset and consistently exercises the least influence. In several instances, an explicit philosophy towards people management does not exist in the organizations. Therefore, an inadequate amount of energy is devoted to the identification of future development needs, and the focus is frequently on the development needs in new or present assignments rather than on the requirements, say, five years into the future.

Many organisations have attempted to meet HRD needs by establishing specialised and centralised sections or departments. The institutionalisation of the HRD function has

undoubtedly had some beneficial effects, particularly in the development of a more rational and coordinated approach to the HRD effort. In this regard, HRD/HRM practitioners have to see themselves as responsible for something more than designing and delivering development programmes, and not as passive providers that others have devised. However, there are some organisations that maintain a generalistic HRM function with a relatively few staff, where HRD is a shared responsibility or seen as the major part of one person's job- the single human resource officer is the only tangible expression of a centralised function. In such organisations, as also pointed out by Megginson et al. (1993), the development function is one of many competing demands on a very limited resource base with implications for the contribution that can be made to HRD. Hence, explanations for the actual status and perceived effectiveness of specific HRD departments have to be sought within their own organisations.

Further, HRM literature gives evidence to a growing tendency towards decentralisation and a concomitant shift towards greater devolvement of responsibility to line management. In the process of decentralisation, there is a substantial sharing of decision-making responsibility of HR activities with line management- sharing in the sense of being a product of consultation between the HR department and line management, rather than being solely with either HR specialists or line management. In the main, primary responsibility remains with the HR department, but line management appears to have more devolved responsibility. The new role of HR specialists has become supporting and facilitating line management in these tasks, not to control them (Hsu and Leat, 2000). Thus, it could be argued that line management responsibility in the areas traditionally held to be the domain of HR specialists is becoming more pervasive (Heraty and Morley, 1998). HRD/MD is no exception. The activities interconnected to MD should be completed through a combination of HR specialist and line management involvement.

However, when the notion of a career for life within the same organisation is not a realistic assumption, the core-linked themes of the HRD perspective are the trend towards individuals taking responsibility for their own learning. In the circumstances, it is much more likely that individual managers have given considerable emphasis to managing their own learning, in identifying their own learning requirements and in finding ways of meeting those. In this regard, to get the maximum benefits out of MD at the organisational level, an appropriate organisational learning climate should be provided, which in turn will contribute to an individual's willingness to learn and transfer learning to the workplace. According to Honey

and Mumford (1989), a favourable climate exists when individuals receive a regular review of performance and learning, and timely feedback on performance and achieved learning, and they are encouraged to identify their own learning needs. Further, according to Twigg and Albon (1992), a proper organisational climate recognises that active learning starts from the top, embraces an open active approach rather than portraying HRD as an expensive “treatment”, and business and HRD managers are operating in partnership (Cunningham 1999). Hence, there should be an organisation-wide commitment and support that is demonstrated by the top-level involvement in learning and in the development of a set of advisors and mentors to support and foster learning.

LIMITATIONS

Understanding the interconnections across seven key dimensions presented in the framework helps to address how MD should be practiced in organizations. However, job analysis information could be useful in HRP and succession planning as it points out areas in which an individual needs to develop in order to further his/her careers. Because of the complexity of the framework, this link is not included. Further, there could be several other HRM dimensions, such as rewards management, recruitment, and selection, which have not been considered, as it makes the framework more complicated. Furthermore, other than HRM dimensions, there could be several other dimensions within an organizational environment that influence MD, such as structure, culture, and the workforce size of the organization, which often influence each other. These, too, have not been considered.

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